

Determination of trace elements in edible fungi by axially view inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry after microwave digestion

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Manuscript received online 24 April 2012, accepted 15 May 2012

Abstract : Eight elements (Fe, Zn, Ca, Mg, Cu, Mn, Ni and Se) were determined in ten species of edible fungus. Trace elements were determined by axially viewed inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) after microwave digestion of the dried samples. The accuracy of the digestion procedures was determined by using standard reference material (GBW 07604-Poplar leaves). The precision and accuracy of determinations were verified through standard addition experiment. The proposed method can be used control and analysis of quality of some fungus samples.

Keywords : ICP-OES, edible fungi, trace elements, microwave digestion.

Introduction

Many species of edible fungi are valuable ingredients in human meal world-wide due to their uniqueness of aroma and taste when cooked. Some fungi are also food to game animals such as deer and stag of the Cervidae family. Edible fungus have been a very popular delicacy especially in some Asian countries and yearly consumption may exceed 10 kg for some individuals¹. Some edible fungus are of medicinal value and especially appreciated in the Asian countries. Apart from some organic nutrients and vitamins, the content of edible fungus could be considered as relatively rich in many mineral constituents². The world of fungi represents a diverse group of organisms and is extremely rich in species diversity. There are plenty of edible fungus which are utilized world-wide and which need a full evaluation of their elemental composition, taking into account their essentiality, non-essentiality and toxicity³. Knowledge of the roles of trace elements in physiology of higher fungi has been limited. Concentrations of the elements in fruiting bodies are generally species-dependent. Substrate composition is an important factor, but great differences exist in the uptake

of individual metals⁴.

Sample pre-treatment appears to be a key step prior to analysis trace elements of natural medicines. In order to eliminate matrix effects and other interference factors, it is necessary to select and optimize digestion method to digest organic materials and convert the analyte into a suitable form for determination. Microwave digestion, wet and dry ashing digestion procedures are commonly used for sample preparation⁵⁻⁸. Wet and dry ashing digestion are not only the most time consuming part during the whole analysis, but also the step in which most errors occur. Microwave digestion is the method of heating samples and digestion solution (various acids) in a closed container using microwave. Reaction in airtight container and microwave heating determine its advantages of complete digestion, rapid and low-blank. Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) is the most used technique in the determination of trace element because of the capability for rapid multi-element detection over a wide concentration range with relatively low detection limits⁹⁻¹¹. Compared to other techniques such as neutron activate analysis (NAA) or inductively coupled

plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)¹²⁻¹⁴, ICP-OES is relatively inexpensive. The combination microwave digestion and ICP-OES has been used to determine element in edible fungi samples, this combination makes it possible to measure the elements in this type of sample in just one single injection, thus reducing the total time of analysis and taking advantage of the increased sensitivity and dynamic range of this technique.

This study aims to establish a rapid, precise and accurate method to determine trace elements in various edible fungus. In addition, microwave digestion procedure as a method of sample preparation was applied to determine of a range of trace elements in edible fungi samples by ICP-OES. The reliability of the method for estimation of trace elements in other samples has been checked by analyzing certified reference and standard addition experiment.

Results and discussion

Analysis of standard reference material :

In order to verify the accuracy of the digestion procedures, a certified reference material GBW 07604-Poplar leaves (China National Research Center for Certified Reference Materials) was used. In the samples, as well as GBW 07604 certified reference material and blank, the quantitative determinations were carried out by a calibration curve obtained by using multi-element standard solutions in which the concentrations of the elements were in the optimal measurement range. Calibration graphs were built from three replicates measurements. The linearity for all elements was satisfied with $R^2 \geq 0.9990$.

In order to validate the microwave digestion procedures, it is necessary to determine a range of elements for which reliable reference values are available. 1.0000 g certified reference material was used. The standard reference material was treated in the same way, which described procedures above. As it can be seen, microwave digestion results are found to be in good agreement with the certified values as in Table 1. The detection limit value defined as the concentration of each element corresponding to three times the standard deviation from the digestion blanks where $n = 10$ was also calculated.

Table 1. Results of the analysis with microwave digestion procedures of GBW 07604-poplar leaves certified reference material ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) ($n = 5$)

Element	Certified value	Determined value ^a
Fe	10.96	10.89 \pm 0.93
Zn	1.48	1.52 \pm 0.47
Mn	1.80	1.79 \pm 0.12
Ca	1.81	1.85 \pm 1.96
Mg	260.00	255 \pm 8
Cu	0.37	0.35 \pm 0.65
Ni	0.076	0.071 \pm 1.08
Se	0.005	BLD

^aMean \pm standard deviation.
BLD : Below the detection limit.

The results of sample analysis :

The concentrations of eight elements determined in each of ten edible fungus are collectively listed in Table 2. It was observed that all edible fungus contained significant values of elements and the element content in the edible fungus presented a wide variability.

Magnesium was the most abundant among the elements quantified and the range of the mean values was between 601.5 (*Tremella*) and 2487.5 (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter. Similar magnesium concentrations were reported in edible fungus investigated by Bakken and Falandysz^{3,15}, and the values in those species ranged between 0.78–1.2 mg/g and 0.6–2.5 mg/g dry matter. Calcium was found to be abundant in some species samples in this study and the range was from 162.7 (*Flammulina velutipes*) to 3222 (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter. Several species are relatively rich in calcium, namely *Pleurotus ostreatus* with 3222 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter and *Auricularia auricula* with 1780.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter, whereas many others contain below 710 $\mu\text{g/g}$ or much less. The four elements zinc, iron, copper and manganese were essential in human nutrition and were quantified in edible fungus. Iron was found to be the most abundant, Colored-mushroom (991.50 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and *Agrocybe aegerita* (565.70 $\mu\text{g/g}$) were richer in iron than the other species, while in a study conducted in the Czech Republic by Randa *et al.* 2050 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Fe dry matter in edible fungus was found¹⁶. In the case of zinc, *Pleurotus ostreatus* con-

Table 2. The results of element contents in edible fungi samples determined ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ($n = 5$)

Analyte	Fe	Zn	Mn	Ca	Mg	Cu	Ni	Se
<i>Auricularia auricula</i>	465.40	31.10	13.50	1780.50	1728.00	6.80	22.51	7.65
Colored-mushroom	991.50	56.95	26.65	702.50	1129.60	15.35	43.55	8.70
<i>Tremella fuciformis</i> berk	383.15	13.35	3.30	432.30	1228.50	6.50	5.45	5.50
<i>Agrocybe aegerita</i>	565.70	55.50	10.70	695.70	1543.90	25.30	30.35	14.70
<i>Tremella</i>	361.55	48.70	3.20	254.60	601.50	4.35	16.50	7.65
<i>Pleurotus pulmonarius</i>	459.05	76.85	13.65	145.31	1452.50	23.30	35.20	5.05
<i>Lentinula edodes</i>	113.45	77.50	20.45	246.50	1454.50	13.50	5.65	6.70
<i>Flammulina velutipes</i>	131.84	70.50	10.90	162.70	1335.90	11.20	8.25	4.05
<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	225.60	156.85	18.90	3222.00	2487.50	23.05	13.90	4.45
<i>Floccularia luteovirens</i>	245.90	134.65	73.65	425.50	2190.70	9.50	6.20	6.85

tained the highest concentration, 156.85 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter and *Floccularia luteovirens* with 134.65 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter. Many others contain below 100 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter. Copper concentrations varied with a range from 4.35 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in the *Tremella* to 25.30 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in *Agrocybe aegerita*. Manganese in the samples varied in a wide range of 3.20 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (*Tremella*)-26.65 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Colored-mushroom). Ni and Se concentrations in the edible fungus indicated similar levels, however Ni level of nearly all edible fungus were relatively higher than Se level. They were determined in the range of 5.45–43.55 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 4.05–14.70 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry matter, respectively. Environmental conditions has been only one of numerous factors affecting element levels in the edible fungus from another perspective, such as the age of mycelium and the interval between fructifications.

The eight elements determined in the study are necessary to human health, the elements are not toxic to human unless they are present in high concentrations. In spite of the fact that the concentration of elements such as Ca, Mg and Fe in the edible fungus seems high. It must be noted that all of the edible fungus considered in this study are not cooked, they were not completely absorbed when cooked.

Method validation :

The method of standard addition was considered as a validation method. In order to demonstrate the validity of the proposed method, the accuracy and recovery study were carried out. A synthetic solution containing Fe, Zn, Mn, Ca, Mg, Cu, Ni and Se was prepared for the performance of the recovery test. The accuracy was evaluated by means of repeatability measures of samples. 2.0 g of the dried *Auricularia auricula* were spiked with the syn-

thetic solution, then the elements were determined following the recommended procedure. As can be seen in Table 3, the results were considered satisfactory. The average recoveries were 92.8% ~ 106.3%. The RSDs were 0.89% ~ 4.83%. It could be concluded that the proposed method was accurate and precise.

Table 3. Results of the accuracy and recovery of the method ($n = 5$)

Element	Blank ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Added ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Detected ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
Fe	465.40	200	660.60	97.60	2.32
Zn	31.10	50	80.20	98.20	3.13
Mn	13.50	10	23.55	100.50	0.89
Ca	1780.50	200	1993.10	106.30	4.78
Mg	1728.00	200	1913.60	92.80	1.52
Cu	6.80	5	11.67	97.30	1.96
Ni	22.51	10	32.82	103.10	2.62
Se	7.65	10	18.07	104.20	4.83

Experimental

Reagents and samples :

All solutions and dilutions were prepared with ultrapure water (18.2 M Ω cm) obtained from an SG Ultra Clear UV Plus system (Wasseraufbereitung und Regenerierstation GmbH, Germany). Analytical grade 65% (w/v) HNO₃ and 30% (w/v) H₂O₂ were used for sample digestion.

The analytical curves were prepared with the following reference solutions : Standard solutions of Fe, Zn, Mn, Ca, Mg and Cu (0.00, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00, 8.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were prepared by diluting of ICP-OES multi-element standard stock solution IV of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 23

elements (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Standard solutions of Ni and Se (0.00, 0.25, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were prepared by diluting of ICP-OES multi-element standard stock solution of VIII 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 9 elements (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany).

Representative edible fungus samples were collected from retail supermarket located in Xinxiang city. The bodies of edible fungus were cleaned of all surface contamination by a stainless steel knife. The bodies were sliced and dried at an ambient temperature in a dustfree room in a manner typical for mushroom preparation for culinary purposes and then powdered. In total, ten samples were collected and analysed.

Apparatus :

The microwave digestion was performed with a CEM MARS-5 closed vessel acid digestion system (CEM, Matthews, NC, USA), equipped with MARS Xpress PTFE advanced composite vessels (internal volume of 55 mL, maximum operating temperature of 300 °C).

The ICP-OES measurements were performed using a Perkin-Elmer Optima 2100 DV inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer Corp., Shelton, Connecticut, USA), equipped with a dual-view plasma torch, a cross-flow nebulizer, a GAST Air Compressor and WinLab32 software. The optimum instrumental settings and operating conditions are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. ICP-OES operational conditions

RF (MHz)	40.68
RF power (W)	1300
Gas flow rate (/min) :	
Plasma gas	15.0
Auxiliary gas	0.2
Nebulizer gas	0.8
Sample uptake rate (mL/min)	1.5
Observation height (mm)	15
Plasma viewing	Axially
Read time (s)	15
Delay time (s)	25
Wash time (s)	25

Sample preparation and analytical procedures :

0.3000 g of an air dried sample was accurately weighed into PTFE vessel, then 11 mL of concentrated HNO_3 and

3 mL of 30% H_2O_2 were poured into PTFE vessel. The vessel was closed, placed on the rotating turntable of the microwave oven and then digestion procedure was started according to the instruction information shown in Table 5. When the digestion program finished, a 20 min ventilation step (no microwave power) cooled the vessels

Table 5. The procedures of microwave digestion

Stage	Power (W)	Heating-up time (t/min)	Operating temperature (T/°C)	Operating time (t/min)
1	800	5	120	5
2	800	3	150	10
3	1600	5	180	15

for reducing the pressure inside to ambient values. After digestion in microwave, the digestion solution was evaporated to dryness on electric hot plate at 140 °C. The residue was transferred into a volumetric flask, and was made up to 25 mL with 3% HNO_3 . Blank test was carried out in the same way.

Each of the edible fungi samples was analysed in triplicate. The determination of the element concentrations was performed using an inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES).

The detection limits of Fe, Zn, Mn, Ca, Mg, Cu, Ni and Se using ICP-OES are 0.0073, 0.0047, 0.0018, 0.0310, 0.0421, 0.0068, 0.0232 and 0.0990 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively.

Conclusion :

Microwave digestion procedure was a simpler, effective, faster, and less contamination procedure of edible fungi samples preparation. Moreover, the proposed method is more suitable for the contents determination of Fe, Zn, Mn, Ca, Mg, Cu, Ni and Se in various edible fungi samples. Trace element contents in edible fungi samples present a wide variability, the presence of trace elements in edible fungi is of particular concern for more specifically their growing environment.

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